

Research Article

Impact of Insecticide Sprays on Soybean Pests and Natural Enemy Densities at Makurdi, Nigeria.

^{*1}Ndam, O.N.; ²Ogunwolu, E. O. and ³Manggoel, W.

^{1,3}Department of Agricultural Technology, College of Agriculture, Garkawa, Plateau State, PMB, 001, Garkawa, Plateau State, Nigeria.

²Department of Crop and Environmental Protection, University of Agriculture, Makurdi.

*Corresponding Author's E-mail: oliverndam@ymail.com, Phone: +2348035864375, +2348065758913

ABSTRACT

Impact of Chlorpyrifos (50g a.i./ha), dimethoate (280g a.i./ha), cypermethrin (75g a.i./ha) and cypermethrin + dimethoate (37.5 + 140g a.i./ha) applied at mid – vegetative, 50% flowering and 50% podding on the population of pest and beneficial insect species on soybean was assessed at the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Agriculture, Makurdi, in 2000 and 2001 cropping seasons. Pest and natural enemy population densities were (i) generally low in both years, and (ii) statistically comparable in sprayed and unsprayed plots. However, in the 2001 cropping season, the number of ants per pitfall trap was significantly ($P<0.05$) higher under chlorpyrifos than under the control at flowering and podding phases of crop growth. The phytophagous species commonly encountered included *Empoasca dolichi* Paoli (492 from D-Vac, 3 from pitfall trap), *Haliticus tibialis* Reut (170 from D-vac, 37 from pitfall trap) and *Cicadella nigrifrons* Dist. (53 from D-vac, 97 from pitfall trap). Natural enemy species were dominated by ants: *Pheidole* sp. (7 from D-vac, 1932 from pitfall trap) and *Camponotus* sp. (1 from D-vac, 80 from pitfall trap). Other predators captured included carabid beetles (72 from pitfall traps only) and spiders. Further studies are needed to confirm low selective pressure of the applied insecticides on beneficial species in soybean.

Keywords: Beneficial insects, phytophagous species, pitfall trap, predators, soybean.

INTRODUCTION

Soybean, *Glycine max* (L.) Merrill was domesticated as early as the eleventh century (Onwueme and Sinha, 1991). It however began to gain importance in terms of number of hectares devoted to its cultivation after the Second World War because of the many uses to which the crop could be put (IITA, 1992). The seed contains high level of edible oil (13-25%) and 40-50% protein suitable for both livestock feed and human consumption (Cobley, 1976). Its role as a protein in human diet almost serves as a replacement of meat which is both insufficient and costly particularly in developing countries (Cobley 1976, Wrigley 1981). In the industrial sector soybeans has been processed into various form including the manufacture of margarine, paint, inks, soaps, insecticides, disinfectants, adhesives and fire fighting foams (Cobley, 1976, Onwuewe and Sinha, 1991).

The world average yield of soybean is 1.7 t ha⁻¹ and African average is 1.1 t ha⁻¹ (FAO, 1989) compared to 0.35 t ha⁻¹ in Nigeria (Bello *et al.*, 1996). Jackai and Singh (1987) and Jackai *et al.* (1990) reported that insect pests are a limiting factor in the production of the crop where it has been cultivated for several centuries. Both the level of pest damage and the wide spectrum of insects have made their control impossible without the use of synthetic chemicals. The impact of insect pest damage on soybean has not attained levels of economic concerns though a wide spectrum of insects are associated with the crop.

In Nigeria Benue State, in the Southern Guinea Savanna ecology, leads in the production of soybean with an over five fold rate of increase in the core production areas of the state between 1985 and 1989 (Ashaye *et al.*, 1974; Woodworth *et al.*, 1992; BNARDA, 1993; BNARDA, 1995). In that part of the country the works of Ogun (1987), Ogunwolu (1992) and Ogunwolu and Ekefan (1996) had addressed the problem of insect pest control in the crop using insecticides. They however, did not consider the natural enemy component of the arthropod fauna associated with soybean. The objective of this study therefore was to assess the impact of the insecticides, recommended for the control of the pest complex of grain legumes, on both the insect pests and their natural enemies in soybean in Makurdi, Benue State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty plots each comprising 10 ridges and 6m long were demarcated in a field that had been ploughed, harrowed and ridged at the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Agriculture, Makurdi (7° 41'N, 8° 37' E). The plots were arranged in randomized complete block design to accommodate four replications of five treatments. Seeds of a medium duration variety of soybean, Samsoy 2, known to be well adapted to Benue State (BNARDA, 1993) were drilled on the crest of ridges on July 13, 2000 and July 17, 2001. Seedlings were thinned at three weeks after planting (WAP) to obtain a density of approximately 266,666 plants per hectare (100cm inter-row and 1cm intra-row spacing).

Treatments consisted of application of chlorpyrifos (50g a.i./ha), dimethoate (280g a.i./ha), cypermethrin (75g a.i./ha), cypermethrin +dimethoate (37.5 + 140g a.i./ha) each at mid – vegetative crop stage (4WAP), 50% flowering (8WAP) and 50% podding (9WAP) using a knapsack sprayer. An untreated plot served as control.

Impact of insecticides on the arthropod fauna of soybean was assessed by comparing the composition and relative abundance of arthropods caught with a suction sampler (Model EA 537-050) as well as pitfall trap in sprayed and unsprayed plots. The funnel of the suction sampler, 10cm in diameter, was dragged above and within the canopy along 4m section of a row at weekly intervals beginning 3WAP. The collections were made between 1500 and 1700h and the specimens were killed with ethyl acetate and preserved in 70% ethanol until sorted for identification.

The pitfall trap was set in the middle ridge of each plot. It consisted of plastic cups, 10cm high and 7cm spout diameter, filled with 50ml of 5% formaldehyde to which a few drops of liquid paraffin were added to reduce surface tension. The rim of the cup flushed with soil surface and soil on either side firmed up to make a gentle slope. Galvanized tripod shield was placed over each cup allowing gap of 2-3cm between rim of cup and sheet. The cups were serviced every 2 weeks. Collections were sorted and sent to the Insect Museum of Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for identification.

Following the method of Salifu (2001), percent reduction using efficacy ratio of the insecticides was computed and transformed to arcsine before analysis of variance. Significantly different means were separated using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (F-LSD) at 5% level of probability (Steel and Torrie, 1960; Obi, 2002).

RESULTS

Relative abundance of arthropod groups caught with D-vac at vegetative and reproductive stages of soybean growth are presented in Table 1. Relative abundance of heteropterous insects using D-vac increased (54.1-60.1%) from the vegetative to reproductive stages of plant growth (Table 1). The coleopteran were the next most abundant, constituting 40.0% and 30.1% of the specimens in the vegetative and reproductive growth stages, respectively. In contrast to heteropterous density the lepidopterous density was the least. Few entomophagous insects were caught. Spiders were the preponderant beneficials and tended to be more abundant at the reproductive stage. The abundance of insect pests on soybean fields monitored by weekly D-vac suction sampling and bi-weekly pitfall trapping during the 2000 and 2001 cropping seasons are presented in Figure 1. The predominant species of insects caught with the suction sampler over the two years included *Empoasca dolichi*, *Monolepta spp*, *Halticus tibialis* and *Cicadella nigrifrons*; while those of the pitfall trap were *Pheidole sp.*, *Camponotus spp*, several species of the family carabidae and lepidopterous larvae in declining order (Fig. 1). The carabid species were *Tachyphanes biplagiatus*, *Tachyphanes amabilis*, *Cicindella melancholica*, *Pheropsophus parallus*, *Stenodindodes sp.*, *Chlaenius caecus*, *Aulacoryssus aciculatus* and *Colliaris laportei*. The bi-weekly pitfall trapping followed the same trend with that of weekly D-vac suction sampling with the mean population of the identified insects in the order *Empoasca dolichi* > *Monolepta spp* > *Halticus tibialis* > *Cicadella spp* > *Pheidole sp* > *Componotus* > Carabids > Lepidopterous larvae. There were no significant differences neither between sprayed and unsprayed plots nor between individual insecticides in terms of percent reduction in the population of both phytophagous insects and beneficial arthropods at all growth stages in the two years of the study (Table 2). The maximum percent reduction was achieved at 50% flowering by dimethoate (52.5%) and by cypermethrin + dimethoate (56.0%) treatments at the same growth stage in 2000 and 2001, respectively.

The effect of sprays on the population density of predaceous beetles, predatory ants and spiders at vegetative and reproductive stages are shown in Table 3. There was a significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) number of predaceous ants per pitfall (129.5 on the average) at the reproductive stage, only in chlorpyrifos sprayed plots, than the unsprayed check (47.5 on the average) in the 2001 cropping season. The population of predaceous beetles and spiders during that season at both the vegetative and reproductive growth stages were similar. The differences in the 2000 arthropod densities at both growth stages were not significant. Scavenging species densities were significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced at vegetative stage in all treatments, except cypermethrin treated plots during 2000 cropping season only. The differences at reproductive stage were not significant, just as those in 2001 at both growth stages

(Table4). In the two years, the number of insect pests species caught by pitfall trap were similar. The collections were, on the average, higher (36.7-49.7 per pitfall) in 2000 than 2001 (28.0-42.0 per pitfall) and also higher at the vegetative than the reproductive stage in both years in all the treatments applied.

DISCUSSION

The population of insect pests and natural enemies was generally low in both years. Since coleopterous species were dominated by the chrysomelid leaf-eating beetles, their slight reduction in numbers during crop reproductive phases, when less fresh vegetation was available, was expected. The population of the hemipterous species, dominated by the cicadellid leafhoppers (nymphs and adults) and the mirid, *Halticus tibialis*, was maintained through growth stages because they were known to feed on both stems and leaves (Anon, 1996) which were available.

The high number of leafhoppers could further be explained by their polyphagous habit. Parh (1983) reported *E. dolichi* on cowpea as its main host with pigeon pea, *Pueraria* sp., soybean, *Amaranthus* sp. and *Centrosema* sp. as alternative hosts. Some of these alternative host plants, including cowpea, in the neighbouring cropped and uncropped fields must have provided a good source of immigrant leafhoppers recorded in this study. The population of *Halticus tibialis* observed here calls for further studies as the report of its presence in Nigeria was on cotton as a potential pest (Anon, 1996).

Ants of the genus *Pheidole* have been known to be predatory to lepidopterous larvae of the fall armyworm (Perfecto, 1991). Their relative abundance at the reproductive stage holds the potential for ants to check lepidopterous pest species that might attack soybean at this growth stage. Perfecto (1991) had recommended the use of ants as a possible component of an integrated pest management programme on maize. The characteristic difference between species caught by the suction sampler and those by the pitfall trap in terms of behavior underscores the need to employ both sampling methods, where mobile canopy foraging species and less mobile, crawling predatory species, respectively might be present.

The low selective pressure of the applied insecticides on beneficial species in soybean may have been due to the uncertainty of the potency of agro-pesticides displayed for sale in our open markets. This poses a fresh research challenge to Entomologists. The overall preponderance of both pest and beneficial arthropods during vegetative and reproductive growth stages of the crop suggests that both luxuriant canopy during the vegetative stage and falling leaves at the reproductive stage tend to provide suitable hiding sites for them.

Table1. Relative abundance of arthropod groups (*Dominant species) caught with D-vac at vegetative and reproductive stages of soybean growth (Pooled data for two cropping seasons)

Arthropod group	Vegetative (3-6WAP)	Reproductive (7-13WAP)
Coleoptera	40.0	30.1
Heteroptera	54.1	60.1
Orthoptera	1.5	3.8
Lepidoptera	0.2	0.4
Diptera	1.5	0.4
Hymenoptera	0.7	2.6
Araneae	2.0	2.6
Total	100.0	100.0

*Dominant species consisted of:

Coleoptera:	<i>Monolepta kraatza</i> , <i>M. nigeriae</i> , <i>Sidorodactylus Sagittarius</i>
Heteroptera:	<i>Halticus tibialis</i> , <i>Empoasca dolichi</i> , <i>Menida maculiventris</i>
Orthoptera:	<i>Catantops annulatus</i>
Lepidoptera:	<i>Eurema brigitta</i>
Diptera:	<i>Mycodrosophila nigrobrunnea</i>
Hymenoptera:	<i>Bracon hebetor</i>
Araneae:	Spider

Table 2. Percent reduction of phytophagous and beneficial arthropods from post-spray D-vac sampling of soybean when sprayed at different growth stages in 2000 1nd 2001 cropping seasons.

Insecticide	Phytophagous 2000			Beneficial 2000		
	Mid-Vegetative (4WAP)	50%flowering (8WAP)	50%podding (9WAP)	Mid-Vegetative (4WAP)	50%flowering (8WAP)	50%podding (9WAP)
Chlorpyrifos (50g a.i./ha)	0.0	45.0	17.6	0.0	0.0	45.0
Dimethoate (280g a.i./ha)	22.5	52.5	31.3	0.0	22.5	22.5
Cypermethrin (75g a.i./ha)	22.5	11.3	40.1	0.0	22.5	0.0
Cypermethrin+Dimethoate (37.5+140g a.i./ha)	22.5	0.0	17.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
Insecticide	Phytophagous 2001			Beneficial 2001		
	Mid-Vegetative (4WAP)	50%flowering (8WAP)	50%podding (9WAP)	Mid-Vegetative (4WAP)	50%flowering (8WAP)	50%podding (9WAP)
Chlorpyrifos (50g a.i./ha)	0.0	34.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Dimethoate (280g a.i./ha)	22.5	45.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Cypermethrin (75g a.i./ha)	11.3	34.0	33.8	0.0	0.0	0.0
Cypermethrin+Dimethoate (37.5+140g a.i./ha)	17.9	56.0	45.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Table 3. Mean number of beneficial arthropods (Predaceous)/pitfall in sprayed and unsprayed soybean plots at Makurdi in 2000 and 2001 cropping seasons.

Insecticides (g a.i./ha)	Beetles	2000			Beetles	2001		
		Ants	Spiders			Ants	Spiders	
		<i>Vegetative</i>	<i>growth</i>	<i>stage</i>				
Chlorpyrifos (50)	3.8	7.2	3.3		1.3	61.0	6.5	
Dimethoate (280)	2.3	11.3	3.0		1.5	37.0	7.3	
Cypermethrin (75)	1.8	5.0	5.3		2.3	61.0	9.0	
Cypermethrin+Dimethoate (37.5+140)	2.0	3.2	5.8		0.8	48.2	7.0	
Unsprayed	2.0	16.5	5.8		1.0	57.5	9.5	
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	
		<i>Reproductive</i>	<i>growth</i>	<i>stage</i>				
Chlorpyrifos (50)	0.8	85.0	3.0		0.5	129.3*	3.5	
Dimethoate (280)	2.0	21.0	5.5		0.0	14.5	3.0	
Cypermethrin (75)	1.5	12.0	7.0		0.5	19.3	5.0	
Cypermethrin+Dimethoate (37.5+140)	2.0	31.0	2.5		1.5	25.8	3.8	
Unsprayed	1.8	9.0	4.3		0.5	47.5	4.3	
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns		ns	61.7	ns	
		<i>Vegetative</i>	<i>+</i>	<i>Reproductive</i>				
Chlorpyrifos (50)	4.5	93.0	6.3		1.8	190.0*	10.0	
Dimethoate (280)	4.3	32.0	8.5		1.5	52.0	10.3	
Cypermethrin (75)	3.3	17.0	12.3		2.8	80.0	14.0	
Cypermethrin+Dimethoate (37.5+140)	4.0	34.0	8.3		2.3	74.0	10.8	
Unsprayed	3.8	26.0	10.0		1.5	105.0	13.8	
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns		ns	80.6	ns	

* = Significant at 5% level of probability; ns = not significant

Table 4. Mean number of insect pest and scavenging species/pitfall trap at different growth stages in sprayed and unsprayed soybean plots in 2000 and 2001 cropping seasons

Insecticide (g a.i./ha)	2000						
	Number of Vegetative(a)	Insect pest/ Pitfall			Number of Vegetative(a)	Scavengers/ Pitfall	
		Reproductive	A	a+b		Reproductive(b)	a+b
Chlorpyrifos (50)	36.5	13.3		49.7	0.5*	2.0	2.5
Dimethoate (280)	22.8	17.3		40.0	0.3*	1.8	2.0
Cypermethrin (75)	32.5	14.5		47.0	2.0	1.8	3.8
Cypermethrin+	27.8	11.5		41.7	0.3*	3.3	3.5
Dimethoate (37.5+140)							
Unsprayed	24.5	12.3		36.7	2.3	3.0	5.3
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns		ns	1.58	ns	ns
2001							
Chlorpyrifos (50)	18.3	9.8		28.0	5.2	2.3	7.5
Dimethoate (280)	27.3	14.8		42.8	12.5	0.5	13.0
Cypermethrin (75)	24.8	10.5		35.2	5.7	1.8	7.5
Cypermethrin+	24.8	15.0		39.7	9.3	3.8	13.0
Dimethoate (37.5+140)							
Unsprayed	25.5	16.0		41.0	7.2	1.3	8.5
LSD (0.05)	ns	ns		ns	ns	ns	ns

* = Significant at 5% level of probability; ns = not significant

Figure 1A: Abundance of insect pests on soybean fields monitored by weekly D-vac suction sampling

VEG.= Vegetative growth stage (3-6WAP), REP.= Reproductive growth stage (7-13WAP)

Figure 1B: Abundance of insect pests on soybean fields monitored by bi-weekly pitfall trapping during the 2000 and 2001 cropping seasons at Makurdi.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The curator, Mr. Matthew Chori, of the Insect Museum, Institute for Agricultural Research, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria is specially appreciated for the identification of insect specimens collected during this study.

REFERENCES

- Anon, 1996. A guide to insect pests of Nigerian crops: Identification, Biology and Control. Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources and the Overseas Development Administration of the British Government. 244pp.
- Bello LL, Ojo AA, Adeyemo MO and Omojor YM, 1996. Effects of planting date on yield components and seed viability in soybean in Southern Guinea savanna, Nigeria. *Afr. Crop Sci. J.*, 4: 393-397.
- BNARDA, 1993. Crop Recommendation for Benue State. Extension Bulletin No. 2. Benue State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority, Makurdi.
- BNARDA, 1995. Annual Report. Benue State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority, Makurdi.
- Cobley LS, 1976. An Introduction to the Biology of Tropical Crops (Second Edition). Longman Publishers, London. 371pp.
- Food and Agricultural Organisation, 1989. Production Yearbook. FAO, Rome Italy.
- IITA, 1992. Sustainable Food Production in Sub-Saharan Africa 1: IITA's Contribution. D. R. Mohan-Raj (ed). IITA, Ibadan, pp 223-231
- Jackai LEN and Singh SR, 1987. Entomological Research on soybeans in Africa. In: Soybean for the Tropics (S.R. Singh, K. O. Rachie and K. E. Dashiell eds.). John Wiley and Sons Ltd, pp 17-24.
- Jackai LEN, Panizzi AR, Kundu GG and Strivastava KP, 1990. Insect pests of soybean in the Tropics. In: Insect pests of tropical legumes (S. R. Singh, ed.). John Wiley and Sons, pp 91 –156.
- Obi IU, 2002. Statistical Methods of detecting differences between treatment means and research methodology issues in laboratory and field experiments. AP Express Publishers Ltd., Nsukka 117pp.

- Ogun FG, 1987. Impact of insecticide application at various soybean growth stages on insect pest abundance, crop damage and yield. Undergraduate project. Department of Crop Production, University of Jos, Makurdi Campus, Nigeria, 36 pp.
- Ogunwolu EO, 1992. Field infestation and damage to soybean and cowpea by pod-sucking bugs in Benue State, Nigeria. *Insect Sci. Applic.*, 13 (6): 801 -805.
- Ogunwolu EO, and Ekefan JE, 1996. Pod-sucking bug damage to cowpea in relation to time and frequency of insecticide application in the Southern Guinea Savanna zone of Nigeria. *J. Agric Technol.* 4(2): 1-9.
- Onwueme IC and Sinha TD, 1991. Field Crop Production in Tropical Africa. Technical Centre for Agricultural and Rural Cooperation (CTA) pp. 337 -343.
- Parh IA, 1983. The Ecology and Distribution of Cowpea leafhopper, *Empoasca dolichi* Paoli in Southwestern Nigeria. *Nig J. Entomol.* 4: 31-38
- Perfecto I, 1990. Ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) as Natural Control Agents of pests in irrigated maize in Nicaragua. *J. Econ. Entomol.* 84 (1): 65-70.
- Steel RGD and Torrie JH, 1960. Principles and Procedures of Statistics with Special Reference to the Biological Sciences. McGraw Hill Book Co. Inc., New York. 481 pp
- Wrigley G, 1981. Tropical Agriculture. The development of Production (Fourth Edition). England ECBS/Longman